

An Equation for the Adsorption of a Solute on the Air/Liquid or Liquid/Liquid Interface and its Application to Relevant Problems

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On the basis of Langmuir's theory, an equation for the adsorption of an electrically neutral solute on the air/liquid or liquid/liquid interface has been derived. Using this isotherm, an expression for the distribution of a solute between two immiscible liquids (molecular weight of the solute remaining constant) has been found in agreement with the Nernst distribution law. Combining this isotherm with that of Gibbs, an equation connecting interfacial tension, γ , with the concentration of the solute in water has been derived. This equation has the same form as the Szyzkowski empirical equation for the lowering of surface tension of aqueous solutions by the lower fatty acids. The application of the isotherm has been extended to the adsorption of surface-active electrolytes at the interface of oil/water. It has been shown that $e\pi/d \log C = 2.302 kT/e = 59 \text{ mV}$ at 25° . The application of the isotherm has also been extended to account for the variation of surface pressure π with the surface area A per molecule of surface-active electrolytes. Correction for the effect of electrical charge has been introduced in two steps by showing (a) that the equation giving π should be multiplied by a factor '2' and (b) that π should be increased by $\Delta\pi$ and finding an expression for the latter (*i.e.* $\Delta\pi$) under certain conditions. The corrected equation has been found to agree fairly with the data obtained by Cockbain on the adsorption of sodium dodecyl sulphate (NaDS) at the *n*-decane/water interface. . .

For the adsorption of gases on the surface of crystalline solids, Langmuir¹ deduced his well-known isotherm from theoretical considerations. He has not, however, extended the application of this equation to the adsorption of a surface-active solute at the interface of a solution. Since at adsorption saturation, the solute molecules form a monolayer at the interface, there can be no inherent objection to the extension of Langmuir's theory to adsorption at an air/liquid or liquid/liquid interface² as would appear from the following considerations.

For a given liquid and a surface-active solute, let n_0 be the maximum number of molecules of the solute which can be adsorbed per unit area of the interface. At equilibrium let n be the number of molecules of the solute in excess, that is, adsorbed per unit area of the interface and let C be its concentration in the solution. Since at equilibrium the rate of adsorption must be equal to the rate of desorption per unit area of the interface, it follows that,

$$\alpha_1 C (n_0 - n) = \alpha_2 n^2 \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

where, α_1 and α_2 are the constants. Hence,

$$K_1 (1 - \theta) C = \theta^2 \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

where $\theta = \frac{n}{n_0}$ and $\frac{\alpha_1}{\alpha_2} = K_1$, the equilibrium constant.

* If t cm be the thickness of the adsorbed layer at the interface, then the equation can also be written as $\alpha_1 C (n_0 - n) / t = \alpha_2 n / t$. Since t cancels out, we have not introduced it.

1. Langmuir, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1916, 38, 2221; 1917, 39, 1848.

2. Vold and Groot, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1962, 66, 1969.

From equation (2) it follows that

$$\theta = \frac{K_1 C}{1 + K_1 C} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

Equation (3) is identical in form with Langmuir's equation for adsorption of gases on a crystalline surface.

Dividing both sides of equation (3) by N , the Avogadro number, and rearranging, we get,

$$\frac{n}{N} = \frac{n_0}{N} \cdot \frac{K_1 C}{1 + K_1 C} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (4)$$

Putting $n_0/N = K_0$ and $n/N = \alpha$, the number of g. mol. of solute adsorbed per unit area of the interface in (4), we get

$$\alpha = \frac{K_0 K_1 C}{1 + K_1 C} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (5)$$

The Distribution of the Solute between Two Liquid Phases

If the interface is that between two immiscible liquids denoted by I and II and if the molecular weight of the solute is the same in I and II, then for the liquid I and the interface we have

$$\alpha = \frac{K_0 K_I C_I}{1 + K_I C_I} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (6)$$

and for the liquid II and the interface we have

$$\alpha = \frac{K_0 K_{II} C_{II}}{1 + K_{II} C_{II}} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (7)$$

Since the interface is common to both I and II, α and K_0 must be the same in equations (6) and (7). It therefore follows that

$$\frac{K_I C_I}{1 + K_I C_I} = \frac{K_{II} C_{II}}{1 + K_{II} C_{II}} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (8)$$

Equation (8) leads to the conclusion that

$$K_I C_I = K_{II} C_{II}$$

or

$$\frac{C_I}{C_{II}} = \frac{K_{II}}{K_I} = \text{a constant} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (9)$$

Equation (9) is thus in agreement with the Nernst distribution law. If S_I and S_{II} be the

solubilities of the solute in the liquids I and II respectively, and if their values are sufficiently small to justify the application of the laws of dilute solution, then it follows that

$$\frac{S_I}{S_{II}} = \frac{C_I}{C_{II}} = \frac{K_{II}}{K_I} \quad \dots \quad (10)$$

Derivation of the Szyszkowski Equation

For a given system it follows from equation (5) and the Gibbs isotherm that

$$a = \frac{K_0 K_1 C}{1 + K_1 C} = - \frac{C}{RT} \left(\frac{d\gamma}{dC} \right) \quad \dots \quad (11)$$

or

$$\frac{K_0 K_1}{1 + K_1 C} = - \frac{1}{RT} \left(\frac{d\gamma}{dC} \right)$$

or

$$\int \frac{K_0 K_1 dC}{1 + K_1 C} = - \int \frac{d\gamma}{RT} + \beta$$

or

$$K_0 \ln (1 + K_1 C) = - \frac{\gamma}{RT} + \beta \quad \dots \quad (12)$$

where β is the integration constant.

When $C = 0$, γ becomes γ_0 , the surface tension of the pure liquid, and the left-hand side equation (12) becomes 0.

Therefore $\beta = \gamma_0 / RT$.

Substituting this value of β in (12), we get

$$\gamma = \gamma_0 - \pi_0 / N. RT 2.302 \log (1 + K_1 C) \quad \dots \quad (13)$$

$$\gamma = \gamma_0 - n_0 kT. 2.302 \log (1 + K_1 C) \quad \dots \quad (14)$$

Szyszkowski^{2a} studied the surface tension of aqueous solutions of propionic, butyric, valeric, and caproic acids and found that the results could be accurately represented by an empirical equation of the form:

$$\gamma = \gamma_0 - (\beta\gamma_0) \log (C/A + 1) \quad \dots \quad (15)$$

where β was found to be constant for all the acids used and A was constant for a given acid but decreased with the increasing length of the hydrocarbon chain of the acids.

If Szyszkowski's equation (15) is compared with equation (14), which has been derived by combining the Gibbs adsorption isotherm and an adsorption isotherm of the Langmuir type, it is found that $\beta\gamma_0 = 2.302 n_0 kT$ and $A = 1/K_1$. Since K_1 varies inversely as the solubility of the solute (vide equation 10), it follows that A decreases as the solubility of the acid decreases and this is in agreement with the observed facts.

Since equation (14) has got a theoretical basis, it should be applicable to all such systems which fulfil the conditions on which it (the equation) is based.

We need hardly mention that in a rigorous treatment, C , the concentration term, should be replaced by the corresponding activity term so that C , wherever it occurs, should be replaced by Cf , f representing the corresponding activity coefficient.

Application to Surface-active Electrolytes

Experiments are in progress to ascertain if equation (14) holds for the adsorption of ions at the interface of two immiscible liquids. The data obtained by A. K. Roy Chowdhury and D. K. Mullik^{a,b}, using cetyltrimethylammonium bromide as solute and *m*-xylene and dilute aqueous solution of HCl as the immiscible liquids, are represented in Fig. 1. The ionic strength of the mixtures of HCl and cetyltrimethylammonium bromide solutions was always maintained at the level 0.01. The HCl was used to suppress hydrolysis and since the concentration of cetyltrimethylammonium bromide in the aqueous solution varied from $5.5 \times 10^{-6} M$ to $3.57 \times 10^{-4} M$ and the HCl was present in relatively large excess, its concentration, and hence activity, might be assumed to remain constant.

FIG. 1

m-Xylene was purified by distillation and the solute was purified by repeated crystallisation from ethanolic solution. Double distilled water and pure HCl were used to prepare the aqueous solutions. The interfacial tension was measured by the method of Bertell and Miller³.

Since O is small, f has been taken as unity. Fig. 1 shows that the plot of γ against $\log C$ is linear and hence '1' can be neglected in comparison to $K_1 C$ in equation (14) when the concentration is not too low. The value of $2.302 \pi_0 kT$ from the slope of the straight line is 22.0. From this π_0 and $1/\pi_0$ are found to be 23.4×10^{14} and $42.7 \text{ \AA}^2$ respectively.

The applicability of equation (14) to adsorption of surface-active compounds points to the conclusion that both the surface-active ion and its satellite counter ion are adsorbed together⁴. Since the area of the CH_2 chain of the surface-active ion is about $20.5 \text{ \AA}^2$ and the area at the interface at adsorption saturation per surface-active ion is found to be about $42.7 \text{ \AA}^2$, that is, slightly more than $2(20.5) \text{ \AA}^2$, we are to conclude that the counter ion is also

2b. Unpublished.

⁴ Adsorbed together means that the adsorption of the surface-active ion causes a counter ion to follow it to the interface.

3. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 50, 1981.

at the interface and the area $42.7 \text{ \AA}^2$ is shared equally by the two ions. It thus appears that even at a concentration of $\text{HCl} = 0.01N$, many of the counter ions (in this case the Cl^- ions) are pushed to the same horizontal plane in which the charged centres of the octyl-trimethylammonium ions lie.

Variation of the Charged Film Potential Φ with the Concentration of the Surface-active Ion in Solution

Crisp⁴ and later Davies⁵ showed that the difference of potential between the charged monolayer at the interface and the interior of the solution varied with the concentration of electrolyte (uni-univalent) according to the equation

$$\frac{d\Phi}{d \log C} = 2.302 \frac{kT}{e} = 0.059 \text{ mV.} \quad \dots (16)$$

This equation can be deduced from equation (14) in the following way:

$$\pi_0 = \gamma_0 - \gamma = n_0 kT \ln(1 + K_1 C) \quad \dots (17)$$

where π_0 is the surface pressure.

$$\frac{d\pi}{dC} = n_0 kT \frac{K_1}{1 + K_1 C}$$

$$\text{or} \quad \frac{Cd\pi}{dC} = n_0 kT \frac{K_1 C}{1 + K_1 C} \quad \dots (18)$$

$$\text{or} \quad \frac{d\pi}{d \ln C} = n_0 kT \frac{K_1 C}{1 + K_1 C} \quad \dots (19)$$

Under equilibrium conditions, if a small virtual change at constant surface area produces a change of $d\pi$ in π_0 and a corresponding change $d\Phi$ in the surface potential, then we can write

$$d\pi = n e d\Phi \quad \dots (20)$$

where n and e represent the number of ions per unit area of the surface and the electronic charge.

Substitution of this value of $d\pi$ into equation (19) with a slight rearrangement leads to

$$\frac{d\Phi}{d \ln C} = \left(\frac{kT}{e} \right) \left(\frac{1}{n} \right) \frac{n_0 K_1 C}{1 + K_1 C} \quad \dots (21)$$

It follows from equation (4) that $n = \frac{n_0 K_1 C}{1 + K_1 C}$

4. "Surface Chemistry", Butterworth, London, 1949, p. 49.

5. *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1951, **A203**, 224.

Substitution of this value of n in equation (21) leads to

$$\frac{d\Phi}{d \log C} = \frac{kT}{e} 2.302 = -59 \text{ mV}$$

for a positively charged surface.

Variation of Surface Pressure π with the Surface Area A

It has already been mentioned (vide equation 17) that

$$\gamma_0 - \gamma = 2.302n_0 kT \log (1 + K_1 C).$$

It follows from equation (5) that

$$\frac{K_1 C}{1 + K_1 C} = \frac{n}{n_0} = \frac{A_0}{A} \quad \dots \quad (22)$$

where $1/n = A$ and $1/n_0 = A_0$, the limiting area at surface saturation. From equation (22) it can be easily shown that

$$\frac{A}{A_0} = 1 + \frac{1}{K_1 C} \quad \text{or} \quad K_1 C = \frac{A_0}{A - A_0}$$

Substitution of this value of $K_1 C$ in equation (17) yields

$$\pi_0 = \gamma_0 - \gamma = 2.302n_0 kT \log A / (A - A_0) \quad \dots \quad (23)$$

This equation† does not take into account the cohesive force between the hydrocarbon chains of the adsorbed ions or the repulsive force between them.

In the oil/water interface, the cohesive force is negligible, as has been pointed out by several authors^{7,8}. In the film at O/W interface, therefore, the effect of electrical repulsion of the adsorbed surface-active ions and their counter ions needs only be taken into consideration. An approximate correction may be introduced in the following way:

To start with, suppose the concentration of the surface-active compound in the solution is C and it is electrically neutral and the number of molecules per unit area at the interface is y_0 and the corresponding pressure π_0 . Let us next imagine that each of the molecules in the film acquires a unit charge, and as a result of this y_0 changes to n . Then we may write⁹,

$$\frac{n}{y_0} = \frac{\pi}{\pi_0} = \frac{S_0}{A} \quad \dots \quad (24)$$

where $S_0 = 1/y_0$ and $A = 1/n$.

† Equation (23) is similar to that of Volmer (*Z. Physik. Chem.*, 1925, 116, 253) and of Frumkin *ibid.*, 1925, 116, 468). Davies and Rideal (*Interfacial Phenomena*, 1963, p. 193) have also stated that it can be obtained from the Gibbs and Langmuir equations.

⁹ π represents the pressure which the n molecules should exert if they were electrically neutral.

$$\text{or } \frac{y_0 - \pi}{y_0} = \frac{\pi_0 - \pi}{\pi_0} = \frac{A - S_0}{A} \quad \dots \quad (25)$$

$$\text{or } \frac{\pi_0 - \pi}{A - S_0} (A - A_0) = \frac{A - A_0}{A} \pi_0 = \Delta\pi \text{ (say)} \quad \dots \quad (26)$$

Since $\Delta\pi$ depends on the activity of the ions, we may put

$$\Delta\pi = \frac{A - A_0}{A} f\pi_0 \quad \dots \quad (27)$$

where f represents the mean activity coefficient of the ions.

Furthermore, it should be noted that when the surfactant is a strong electrolyte (uni-univalent) then at adsorption saturation there must be present π_0 surface-active ions and π_0 counter ions per unit area of the interface and each of them must exert the same lateral pressure. Therefore, both the sides of equation (23) should be multiplied by the factor '2' and the final expression for surface pressure should be

$$\pi = 2\pi_0 + \frac{A - A_0}{A} f\pi_0 \quad \dots \quad (28)$$

$$= 2.302 (2\pi_0 kT) \left(1 + \frac{A - A_0}{2A} f\right) \log \left(\frac{A}{A - A_0}\right) \quad \dots \quad (29)$$

The introduction of a factor 1.8 has been suggested previously by Alexander and Teorell⁶ for charged monolayers. Davies⁷ found that for charged gaseous films at very low values of concentration, C , of an uni-univalent electrolyte, the factor should be '3'. The closest possible approach to the plane containing the charged centres of the surface-active ions of the film by the counter ions has been discussed by several authors^{8,9}. Cockbain¹⁰ has studied the adsorption of sodium dodecyl sulphate (NaLS) on *n*-decane/water interface at 20°. Some of his data are recorded in Tables I and II along with the values of π observed by him, and those calculated from equation (29) taking $f = 1$.

TABLE I

NaLS (moles/l).	A/mol.	Interfacial pressure (dynes/cm).	
		Obs.	Calc. from eq. 29.
0.0014000	41.5 Å ²	46.1	
0.0006940	47.2	39.6	43.3
0.0003470	52.4	33.9	33.3
0.0001730	57.1	28.6	28.5
0.0000867	61.7	23.8	23.1

N.B. The value of $A_0 = 41.5 \text{ Å}^2$ has been used in equation (29).

6. *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1939, **35**, 727, 792.

7. Askew and Danielli, *ibid.*, 1940, **36**, 785.

8. Davies and Rideal *J. Colloid Sci. Supplement*, 1954, **1**, 1.

9. Haydon, "Recent Progress in Surface Science," 1964, **1**, 92.

10. *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1954, **50**, 874.

TABLE II

NaLS (moles/l).	A /mol.	Interfacial pressure (dynes/cm).	
		Obs.	Calc. from eq. 29.
0.0079000	48.8 $\text{\AA}$ ^a	42.8	41.7
0.0069400	49.1	40.5	40.9
0.0052100	50.8	36.0	35.3
0.003470	56.8	30.5	29.5
0.001735	69.4	23.0	21.4

N.B.— $A_0 = 42.8 \text{\AA}^2$ has been used in equation (29).

In presence of 0.1 *M*-NaCl Cockbain¹⁰ found the o.m.c. of the (NaLS) sample used, was 0.0014 *M* and at the saturation point, the value of $A_0 = 41.5 \text{\AA}^2$. Taking this value of A_0 , we have calculated the corrected value of π , using equation (20). These are recorded in column 4 of Table I. It will be noticed that there is fair agreement between the observed and the calculated values of π .

In Table II are recorded the data of (NaLS) in absence of NaCl. The value of A_0 used here is the average of $41.5 \text{\AA}^2$ and $44.8 \text{\AA}^2$ as at the saturation point of the interface, in the absence of salt, the area/molecule was found to be nearly $44.8 \text{\AA}^2$. The values of surface area A , recorded in column 2 of Table II, were obtained by Cockbain from measurements of adsorption of (NaLS) on the surface of emulsion globules of *n*-decane in water and according to his own indication these are quite accurate. It may be noticed that in this case also there is fair agreement between the observed and the calculated values of π , although no NaCl was used.

It has already been mentioned that the surface-active ion and its counter ion are adsorbed together. This also follows from Gibb's theory, according to which the interface as a whole should be electrically neutral. The net effect therefore is as if a molecule of the surface-active compound is adsorbed and not much electrical work is involved in the process even when the surfactant is a strong electrolyte.

It may be pointed out further that for the surface-active compounds (NaLS) and cetyltrimethylammonium bromide, a surface-active ion and its counter ion together at adsorption saturation occupy an area of about $42 \text{\AA}^2$ at the interface. If, t , be the thickness of the interface in ($\text{\AA}$) then a cell of volume $42 \times t \text{\AA}^3$ contains a surface-active ion and its counter ion.

It may also be noted that when $A \gg A_0$, $2.302 \log A/(A - A_0)$ reduces to $A_0/(A - A_0)$ and equation (29) assumes the form $\pi (A - A_0) = 3 kT$. This is in agreement with the equation of Davies⁵ for the limiting case $A \gg A_0$.

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